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Final Essay: Sino-American Rivalry in Cambodia: the Arising Cambodian – US Controversy on a Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) Project in Cambodia's Coastal Areas.

I. Introduction

This paperwork notices the significance of current dynamic foreign relations of Cambodia in the last few decades, especially with People's Republic of China (China). It also notices the importance of rapid China Rise, and the establishment of One Belt One Road or Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) by Chinese President Xi Jing Ping in 2013. Responding to this phenomenon, Cambodian government has no hesitation to supports this mega plan. At the same time, there are also critical concerns about negative impacts of the BRI implementation on not only Cambodia's economy and society but also foreign relations. For the United States (US), that scenario poses a potential threat to US's national interests and regional stability in Southeast Asia. This kind of contradicting views on BRI is also simultaneously happening in other small states that are orbiting around BRI gravitation.

A number of studies have conducted concerning on the BRI's impacts on Cambodia in general. On one hand, a group of scholars optimistically see the BRI is the catalyst boosting Cambodia economic growth, technological development, physical infrastructure enhancement, regional integrations, and connectivity (Chheang, 2017 ;Sok, 2019; Heng, 2019; Sorn & Hor, 2019). On the other hands, there is a big concern about debt trap, falling into Chinese political orbit, environmental impacts, social discontents and questioning on ASEAN centrality validity (Qi, 2018; Keo, 2019; Cheunboran, 2019; Mao & Ngoun, 2019;). Specifically, this study focuses only Cambodia relations with US and China. Scholarly discussions figure out that both US and China are vital for Cambodia. They suggest that Cambodia better diversifying relations not only with China or US but also with other alternative powers (Heng S. , 2014; Cheunboran , 2015; Var, 2015; Heng, 2019; Sim, 2019).

What are the motives behind US's concerns on a Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) Project in Cambodia's Coastal Provinces? This essay mainly aims to define factors contribute to the rising of verbal tensions between Phnom Penh and Washington on the allegation on secret agreement of Chinese military bases in Cambodia's coastal areas. Koh Kong development plan is used as a case study. This mini research also seeks for practical implications for minimizing risks from the BRI. Rational Choice Theory is the conceptual framework in explaining this paper. Also, state is the sole actor in decision making process. In international relations, states rationally make decisions for maximize their national interests. There are no true friends nor last long enemies but national interests. In this essay, economic development, diplomatic supports, and strategic security are the dimensions in analysing Cambodia relations with both China and US.

II. Discussions and Empirical Analysis

1. Cambodia – China relations

Sino-Cambodia relation is traditionally rooted since the ancient time of tributary system (Mahbubani & Sng, 2017). The two countries' relations was upgraded to comprehensive strategic partnership in 2010 (China and Cambodia, 2013).

Firstly, China is playing a leading role in developing Cambodia. Under the BRI framework, many physical infrastructure projects such as hydropower dams, expressways, railroads, bridges, seaports, airports, and other kind of infrastructures are under constructing and planning. Economically, China has substituted Japan as the biggest source of foreign direct investment (FDI), loan and aid to Cambodia. Just in 2018 alone, Chinese FDI accounted for \$3.1 billion. From 2013 to 2017, capitals flew from China accounted for \$5.3 billion. In 2017, the two countries trade amounted \$6 billion, and aim to reach \$10 billion in 2023. Early this year, China has agreed providing Cambodia \$588 million aid and importing 400,000 tons milled rice (Heng, 2019). So, good relations with China have generated huge mutual benefits for both countries. While Cambodia got developed, China got access to Cambodian market and the support of BRI from Cambodia. Coincidentally, the European Union (EU) already put tariffs on Cambodian rice exportation to EU market (ZX, 2019) , and EU has also started the process of lifting out trade preferences “Everything But Arm (EBA)” from Cambodia (Heng, 2019).

Secondly, to survive and prospered in this anarchic world order a small and weak Cambodia needs make more friends as much as possible (Heng S., 2014; Cheunboran , and 2015; Var, 2015). China is traditional friendly neighbour of Cambodia; Cambodia and China need each other in this globalized world (Chheang, 2017). In multilateral cooperation, the two countries cooperate and support each other such as in the United Nations, ASEAN, Asia Regional Forum, Great Mekong Subregion, and so on. It is reciprocal gain and positive sum-game.

Thirdly, Cambodia strategically needs to engage with alternative superpowers for power balancing and security (Cheunboran , 2015). Cambodia is located between two countries which are historically competing to control Cambodia namely Thailand and Vietnam. The border dispute erupted in 2008 between the two kingdoms on Preah Vihear temple area shows less trust in Cambodian -Thai relations. How about the east border? Currently, Phnom Penh and Hanoi see each other as good neighbours. However, the Statement of ASEAN Summit was unable to release due to South China Sea disputes when Cambodia was an ASEAN Chair in 2012. This triggered anger from Vietnam and some ASEAN members who opposed Chinese claims (Cheunboran , 2015). Likewise, being close with Cambodia, China can play a significant role in ASEAN, reduce the US influence in Southeast Asia, and protect Chinese national interest. For instance, agreement on sending back “anti-Chinese Muslim Uyghur” to China in 2009 (Var, 2015) , above said ASEAN issues, and counterbalancing the American-Vietnamese close relations are Chinese gains.

2. Cambodia- US relations

The diplomatic relations between Cambodia and United States was first ever established since 1950 (U.S. Department of State). This contentious relations experienced cut off, and re-established in 1993 (U.S. Relations With Cambodia). Why?

Economically, US has less interest in Cambodia. The population and market size are small. Cambodia's skilled labours are less far behind other countries' in the region. US is a big market for Cambodian products. In 2018, bilateral trade reached \$4.3 billion. Yet, US could export only \$447 million to Cambodia (Cambodia: U.S.- Cambodia Trade Facts). Cambodia has benefited economically from US' Generalized System of Preferences (GSP) which now US is considering of removing out due to unrespecting labour rights and democracy principles (HUTT, 2019). U.S. provided \$77.6 million of aid in 2014 (U.S. Relations With Cambodia). US aid is always accompanied by US political demands that Cambodia rarely follows.

Diplomatically, so far there is less exchange of high level official visits between the two countries. Moreover, the tension between two countries has risen up when US government restricted in issuing visa to Cambodian high ranking officials due to the violations of human rights and undermining democracy (NAUERT, 2017). US wants Cambodia to respect their values. Yet, Cambodia denied, and tends to cooperate closely with China. This has escalated US speculation on Sino-Cambodian ties.

Geopolitically, Cambodia is strategically less important for US if compared to the Philippines or Vietnam. Likewise, US is far away from Cambodia in case Cambodia need helps. The Cambodian – American tie is still affected by the suffering experiences of Cambodian people because of US manoeuvre during the 1760s, 70s and 80s (BULUT, 2017). Weak Cambodia cannot contest with China, but Vietnam does. Both US and Vietnam have a common interest is opposing China rise, especially in Southeast Asia.

3. Comparison US and China Relations with Cambodia

In short, from the economic dimension both US and China are important for Cambodia's economic growth. China is largest investor while US is the most valuable customer. However, newly graduated lower-middle income Cambodia prefers Chinese ODA and investment without condition rather than US or EU. From diplomatic relations angle, Cambodian – American relations not yet good if compare to Sino-Cambodian comprehensive strategic partnership cooperation relations. Lastly, from strategic security perspective US pays much attention on its allies not Cambodia for containing China. The China rise and close relations Cambodia poses threat to US interests in Southeast Asia.

4. Case study: BIR project in Koh Kong development project

Recently, the rhetorical tension has erupted after releasing of a report of Wall Street Journal concerning on a deal of secret agreement between Phnom Penh government and Beijing administration. According to unanimous US officers, that agreement allows Chinese army to

access Ream naval base for 30 years with every decade renewals (Page, Lubold , & Taylor, 2019). Not far from the naval base, there is the serious concern from US on a multi development project under BRI themes constructed by “Tianjin Union Development Group (UDG)”. In 2008, Cambodian authority granted UDG the 99 years lease. UDG is working on the deep seaport, airport and city; it covers the area of 45, 000 hectares which is equal to 20% of Cambodia’s coastline with planned \$3.8 billion cost (Crispin, 2018).

After refusing US’ offer on repairing the military facilities in Ream Naval Base, and the suspicion on UDG’s project, US requested Cambodia’s clarification on the concerned issue (Thul, 2019). Why is it matter? First, the United States has less trust on China and Cambodia. Cambodia immediately responded that there is no Chinese military base on Cambodia’s soil, and it is contradict to the permanent neutrality principle stipulated in the constitution. Until now, Hun Sen is strongly adhering his refusal (Clarification of Samdech Akka Moha Sena Padei Techo Hun Sen, Prime Minister of the Kingdom of Cambodia, 2019). China also affirmed with Cambodia’s response (Spokesperson's Remarks, 2019). Yet, US is not satisfied. The above mega project has accelerated both countries economic growth and tightened relations, while US is threatening to take away GSP from the less interesting Cambodia, and concerning more about Chinese deep involvement in Cambodia.

Secondly, US is in Thucydides Trap while China is not. The ruling power “US” has approximately 800 military bases worldwide, while the rising power “China” just has only one in Djibouti in 2017 (Page, Lubold , & Taylor, 2019). The over speculation of future Chinese military base in Cambodia makes no sense. Thucydides trap is applicable from American government perspectives. US overthinking and feels unsecured about the Chinese capability. China seeks to realize their dream of being wealthy and powerful. Yet, China has tried not to project their ambition to be world hegemon or changing current world order (ALLISON, 2015). In contrast, what Beijing wants is stability and cooperation with other countries.

Thirdly, close Sino-Cambodia relations harms to US interest in the region. Strategically, the UDG development project is the standpoint that enhances Chinese influence; affect the US’ strategic interest in the region (Page, Lubold , & Taylor, 2019). If US’ allegation is true, ASEAN will face instability and separation. Is it US’ tactic for deteriorating the situation and winning other ASEAN members’ support who tend to be careful with China? For sure that US needs other potential Southeast Asia states for containing China Rise and protecting US national interests (free military navigation in South China Sea, accessing maritime trade route, etc.). It is also the same for China. Chinese government prioritizes peace, yet China will take action immediately if US go across red line (CGTN, 2017).

III. Conclusion

Cambodia used to suffer seriously from superpowers’ rivalry. During Cold War, Cambodia was the ideological laboratory of the West and the East. That experiment resulted in devastations and tragedy for Cambodian people. Small states have less bargain power with the world hegemons. In fact, Cambodia tried hard not to take side in order to prevent East-

West confrontation. Ultimately, Cambodia became world powers' battlefields. The current situation in the coastal areas remains me Cambodia's bitter experiences with superpowers. Since 1993, Cambodia shall be permanently neutral according to Article 53 of Cambodian Constitution. All countries are friends of Cambodia. The currently relations with US and China is defined by economic opportunities, mutual supports, and common security. Cambodia never gives up neither US nor China. Both countries have played a significant role in contemporary Cambodian history and development. Cambodia's relation with China is better than US because the Cambodian-Chinese mutual interests bigger the Cambodian-American. To survive and benefit in this anarchic world order no matter liberal world order or Sino-centric world order, Cambodia needs to be very flexible. Adhering neutrality, increasing friendly foreign relations, balancing external powers' influences, improving self-reliance and producing more skilful diplomats are needed.

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